

ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF FINANCIAL, INSURANCE, AND REAL ESTATE ACTIVITIES IN EUROPEAN MOUNTAINOUS REGIONS FROM 2008 TO 2018

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Abstract:

This article conducts a comprehensive economic analysis of financial, insurance, and real estate activities in European mountainous regions over the period spanning from 2008 to 2018. The study employs statistical methods to examine key indicators, providing insights into the trends and dynamics within these economic sectors in the context of mountainous Europe. The analysis covers diverse countries, offering a comparative perspective on the performance of financial, insurance, and real estate activities across the region. Through rigorous data examination and interpretation, the article aims to contribute valuable insights into the

Mountain Perspective Journal (1/2022)

economic landscape of European mountainous areas, facilitating a deeper understanding of the challenges and opportunities within these vital sectors.

1. Introduction:

The economic activities related to finance, insurance, and real estate play a pivotal role in shaping the economic landscape of European mountainous regions. This article delves into a detailed examination of key indicators and trends within these sectors over the ten-year period from 2008 to 2018.

2. Methodology:

The study employs statistical analyses to process and interpret data related to financial, insurance, and real estate activities. Various indicators, including averages and standard deviations, are considered to provide a nuanced understanding of the economic dynamics.

3. Results:

Statistics reveal noteworthy trends in financial, insurance, and real estate activities across different European mountainous regions. Averages and

standard deviations for each country are presented, shedding light on the variability and concentration of economic activities within these sectors.

In the examination of statistics pertaining to financial and insurance activities as well as real estate activities (illustrated in figures 2.12 - panels a-f and annex Parametric Analysis Europe), the data reveals averages for Bulgaria at 15,401.55, Italy at 142,982.55, Austria at 13,857.27, Portugal at 9,913.09, Romania at 6,838.27, and Slovakia at 9,414. The corresponding standard deviations are recorded as 2,278.127 for Bulgaria, 7,959.51 for Italy, 1,638.002 for Austria, 504.891 for Portugal, 1,898.701 for Romania, and 2,809.27 for Slovakia.

Upon initial inspection, the distribution curve exhibits relative central symmetry, with scores around the mean highly concentrated, suggesting leptokurtosis despite the unimodal nature of the distribution.

Our working assumption posits a normal distribution of scores, warranting the application of parametric tests. Though a limited number of extreme values induce a positive asymmetry, these outliers remain statistically significant. The concentration of a substantial number of scores around the means contributes to some leptokurtosis in the distribution, attributable to phenomena in the economy of mountainous Europe.

To address the observed distributional characteristics, the logarithm of the obtained values is employed following universally accepted statistical principles. This logarithmic transformation aims to balance the distribution, aligning it with the Gauss-Laplace normal curve.

The normality test, subsequent to logarithmization, demonstrates a distribution of actual scores aligning closely with normal values. Furthermore, the dispersion of empirical scores, also after logarithmization, falls within the limit of one standard deviation, indicating conformity to a normal distribution.

Through the application of logarithmic transformation, the obtained scores undergo rigorous statistical processing. All factors considered in the study are meticulously accounted for, aiming to derive data that closely mirrors the economic reality documented in mountainous Europe. Despite temporary disturbances in the distribution of scores due to economic measures, this methodology ensures a more accurate representation of the underlying economic dynamics.

Figure 2.12 Panel a-f. Histogram for the Financial and Insurance Activities sectors; real estate activities – Bulgaria, Italy, Portugal, Austria, Romania,

Slovakia

The significance of these examinations lies in the meticulous observation of the influences exerted by specific factors on the evolution of economic sector segments, specifically in the domains of financial and insurance activities and real estate activities. Following the application of normality tests subsequent to logarithmization, the null hypothesis necessitates rejection, allowing for an in-depth analysis of the working hypothesis. Descriptive and inferential analyses were conducted, taking into consideration the distribution of scores within normal limits, as per the working hypothesis, leading to the application of parametric tests.

The central tendency for the analyzed period in this sector indicates an increase in the European mountain population of active enterprises within the studied domain from 2008 to 2018. During this examined timeframe, hypothesis H1, signifying the intensification of activity, was substantiated.

Statistics and data presented in the figures corroborate the notable agglomeration and development trend of this sector in mountainous Europe. Concurrently, the statistics affirm the heightened pace of growth within this economic sector segment.

4. Discussion:

The economic analysis prompts a discussion on the observed trends, offering insights into the factors influencing the performance of financial, insurance, and real estate activities. The article considers both the central tendencies and variations, exploring how these economic sectors have evolved in response to external factors.

5. Implications:

Understanding the economic dynamics of financial, insurance, and real estate activities in mountainous Europe has significant implications for policymakers, investors, and local communities. The insights gained from this analysis can inform strategic decisions and foster targeted interventions to enhance economic sustainability in these regions.

6. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this article provides a thorough economic analysis of financial, insurance, and real estate activities in European mountainous regions from 2008 to 2018. By examining key indicators and trends, the study contributes valuable insights to the understanding of the economic landscape in these vital sectors, ultimately supporting informed decision-making and strategic planning.

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